

FUNDAMENTALS OF USING INNOVATION IN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES.

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***Abstract.** The article shows new innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process, new information in the field of education and effectively using them in creative work.*

Introduction

The comprehensive development and progress of the society depends on the development and improvement of the content of education.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev stated in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, "**...it is necessary to introduce information technologies that fully meet international standards at all stages of education.**" That's why we should try to make the young generation mature in all aspects.

In contrast to the methodical lesson development of the educational process focused on the active, effective activity of the teacher, the pedagogical technology of education focuses on learners, and also creates conditions for mastering the educational material, taking into account their individual and joint activities with the teacher.

Each of the educational technologies embodies information materials about the conditions of the educational session, pedagogical goals, tasks and expected results, the plan of the educational session, methods and means of teaching. It also includes a technological map of the training session, that is, a step-by-step description of the cooperative activity of the teacher and the student according to the goal of this training session.

New innovative educational technologies, modern methods and tools of teaching are entering the educational process and are being used effectively. The teacher should not be the only source of learning, but should be the organizer of the process of students' independent work, consultant, manager of the learning process. It is these ideas that underlie the development of innovative educational technology.

The main goal of education is to increase the effectiveness of education based on the use of elements of innovative educational technologies, to create independent thinking, original specialists.

The current educational development brought a new direction - innovative pedagogy to the field. The term "innovative pedagogy" and its characteristic research appeared in Western Europe and the United States in the 60s.

Innovation (English innovation) is innovation. Innovation means purposeful changes that introduce new, relatively stable elements into a certain social unit. This is the activity of the innovator.

Lectures as effective forms of organizing training sessions (problematic lecture, lecture-seminar, virtual-technological lecture, visual lecture, binary lecture, introductory lecture, lecture-conference, informative lecture, lecture-debate, explanatory lecture, on-Line lecture) training, video training, webinars, internet conferences, as innovative teaching

methods, problem methods, interactive methods, practical games, educational projects, portfolios, graphic organizers, information and communication technologies are needed.

It is known that pedagogical technology is an educational process that is pre-planned and fully designed in the educational process, designed for a certain time, the educational process is more focused on the learner, using activated methods and modern educational tools, which guarantees the achievement of the educational goal.

Live speech of the pedagogue, games of individuals, public actions serve as a means of education. But in order to solve the relevant educational tasks, it is necessary to include them in a specific system of the work of a coach and pedagogue. The effectiveness of the educational result depends on the skillful use of the methods, tools and forms of organizing the educational process and ensuring their harmony.

When using technologies, we should pay attention to the work of monitoring the student's knowledge, comparing the important things in their growth with the main ideas that have arisen in society, determining the ways and methods of their development, choosing the appropriate one, and deeply analyzing the dialectics of the mutual transition of various tools and methods of educational influence.

Today, educational technologies are divided into the following areas:

1. Modern-traditional teaching elements are used pedagogical technologies;
2. Person-oriented pedagogical technologies in the pedagogical process;
3. Pedagogical technologies based on activation and acceleration of students' activities;
4. Pedagogical technology based on effective management of the educational process;
6. Developing educational technologies;
7. Technologies related to private educational subjects.

When innovative education technologies are used, students' interest increases, knowledge turns into skills, and the quality and efficiency of knowledge increases.

It is known that primary education creates a basis for the development of mental and spiritual qualities of students. Growing and developing the consciousness, thinking, worldview and spiritual world of the individual through the means of knowledge given to the child during this period is one of the main manifestations of organizing the child's development process in education.

In primary education, the necessary knowledge is imparted on the basis of practical activities and various interesting tools. In the process of this activity, the child, who is developed by the student's ability to achieve some result, imagine through images, create something with his own hands, begins to understand his self.

Therefore, in modern conditions, the use of project and problem-based educational technologies in educational practice develops students' ability to think independently, critically and creatively, while ensuring the effective course of the teaching process. The social requirements for improving the quality of education and increasing its effectiveness require teachers to use project and innovative educational technologies in the process of teaching purposefully and effectively.

Educational technology is based on the principles of humanity. The uniqueness of this direction in philosophy, pedagogy and psychology is shown by paying special attention to the individuality of the student.

- Taking into account the innovative development features of modern educational

methods, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the following principles in education:

- the principle of education based on structural-functional reformation;
- the principle of ensuring mutual compatibility of economic and social goals in the educational process;
- the principle of effectiveness in financing education;
- the principle of taking into account the specific features of socio-economic development between the market of labor and educational services.

Thus, based on the above-mentioned approaches, we have developed recommendations aimed at effective use of innovative educational methods in the educational process;

1. When using modern educational methods, paying special attention to the organizational and technological criteria that take into account the level of education, organizing the educational process by dividing the factors affecting various forms and methods of education into separate groups;

2. Ensuring the gradation of the use of educational methods that develop a person in obtaining a certain level of knowledge, taking into account the requirements based on the joint interests of the participants in education

3. Taking into account educational and professional flexibility in education, which reflects specific development characteristics of the learner, limits the development of the education system in some cases and reveals its role in society;

4. Showing the formation of a person's social role as a result of the educational process; use of educational methods that are not influenced by factors that lead to the stratification of psychological and professional knowledge.

5. The educational process can be viewed as an asymmetric information base, because the real assessment of the quality of the educational process is valid after a certain period has passed. Based on this situation, it is appropriate to use multi-developmental educational methods.

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